

Transformative Research Challenge-2024 Research Proposal Food Loss and Waste

Names and family names of team members:

Alice Diana
Abu Sayed
Yara van Halteren

Name of the lead contact for communication purposes:

Alice Diana

Name of university or research center:

Sapienza Università di Roma
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Email address:

alice.diana@studenti.unipd.it
a.sayedpstu@gmail.com
yaravanhalteren@hotmail.com

Research Project Description

Short title of proposed research project: (up to 5 words)

Surplus Food Stores: Implementation Strategies

Research Summary and Abstract: (Up to 500 words)

Food waste is a critical global issue with significant economic, environmental, and social implications. Annually, approximately one-third of all food produced is wasted, leading to economic losses, food insecurity, and environmental degradation (FAO, 2011). The retail sector plays a crucial role in addressing this problem. “Surplus food stores”, or “food waste supermarkets,” are emerging as an innovative solution. These stores sell surplus, overproduced, mislabelled, or near-expiry products at reduced prices, thereby mitigating food waste and providing affordable food options.

Countries such as Belgium, Denmark, and the United Kingdom have already successfully implemented surplus food stores, demonstrating their effectiveness in reducing food waste, enhancing food access for low-income communities, and promoting sustainable consumption patterns (Let's SaveFood, 2021; Saxena et al., 2018; WeFood, 2016). However, broader adoption of these initiatives is hindered by gaps in policy frameworks and varying implementation success across the world.

This research seeks to bridge these gaps by investigating the policies and strategies surrounding surplus food stores and their social impacts. A mixed-methods approach will be

applied, encompassing a literature review, policy analysis, and surveys with the surplus food store owners to identify the key factors contributing to the success of these initiatives. Using the Positive Deviance Model, the study will analyze successful case studies to investigate current policies and regulations affecting surplus food store implementation across the globe. Integratively, actionable recommendations will be formulated based on the study findings to reduce food waste and promote global sustainability. By exploring the interplay between policy frameworks, implementation strategies, and social impacts, this research aims to provide insights to policymakers, businesses, and community stakeholders regarding the potential of surplus food stores to mitigate food waste and promote sustainable practices. Ultimately, this project aims to enhance global efforts toward food waste reduction and contribute to achieving sustainable goals.

Background: (Up to 500 words)

Globally, an estimated 10% of the world's food, totaling over 540 million tons, is lost at the retail level. This underscores the necessity for targeted strategies and policies to address these specific stages of the food supply chain (FAO, 2019). Reducing food waste at the retail level is critical for enhancing food security, sustainability, and environmental stewardship as retailers are uniquely positioned to promote food waste reduction by minimizing waste and influencing consumer behaviors (FAO, 2019; LinkRetail, 2023).

Establishing "surplus food stores" or "food waste supermarkets" is a promising approach to tackling retail food waste (Riesenegger et al., 2023). These retail outlets sell surplus, overproduced, mislabelled, near-expiry, or overall unsold food products at reduced prices, thereby reducing waste and increasing access to nutritious food. The implementation of such stores has demonstrated significant positive impacts in multiple countries, including Denmark, Belgium, and the United Kingdom (Kulikovskaja, 2017; LetsSaveFood, 2021; Pace, 2018; Saxena et al, 2018; WeFood, 2016). Key strategies for food waste reduction include advanced inventory management, better consumer demand forecasting, and enhanced consumer education. Furthermore, retailers can implement dynamic pricing strategies to facilitate the sale of surplus or near-expiry products at reduced prices. This not only reduces waste but also provides cost-effective options for consumers. (Pimentel et al, 2022)

For businesses, reducing food waste leads to significant cost savings through improved efficiency and reduced waste disposal expenses. Moreover, it enhances corporate reputation by demonstrating a commitment to sustainability and social responsibility. Additionally, this suggested strategy for food waste reduction can significantly benefit consumers, particularly those from low-income communities, by increasing access to affordable and nutritious food. Moreover, it will raise awareness and promote the adoption of sustainable consumption patterns through education on food storage and waste reduction.(Pimentel et al, 2022).

Effective policies are essential for reducing food waste at the retail level. They encourage practices that minimize waste and promote food recovery, benefiting businesses and communities. For instance, governments can incentivize businesses to donate surplus food rather than dispose of it unnecessarily. Public-private partnerships further enhance these efforts by fostering collaboration between retailers and surplus food stores. These collaborative approaches promote innovative solutions and inspire action across the food value chain, ensuring more efficient distribution of surplus food, minimizing food waste, and

contributing to sustainable food systems and environmental stewardship (Pimentel et al, 2022).

Research Methodology: (Up to 500 words)

Research Design

This study will adopt a Positive Deviance Model (PDM) approach to successful case studies to comprehensively analyze policies, implementation strategies, and social impacts related to surplus food stores. The research design is structured into three stages: literature and policy review, case studies, and synthesizing findings into actionable guidelines and recommendations through a comprehensive report.

Stage 1: Literature and Policy Review

The research starts with a systematic literature review (SLR) to gain a thorough understanding of existing surplus food stores, food waste, and relevant policies. This review encompasses academic journals, relevant retail trade literature, and corporate data, using keywords such as "surplus food," "food waste," "policy," "social impact," "retail food waste," and "food recovery". We will also conduct a comprehensive policy analysis on global national legal frameworks regarding food waste to identify local regulatory barriers to food waste redistribution and assess successful implementation opportunities and strategies. AI-powered translation tools and software will be utilized when necessary to ensure a comprehensive understanding of literature and policies from different languages.

Stage 2: Selection of Case Studies and Analysis

Case studies of successful implementation of surplus food stores around the world will be selected based on relevance, data availability, and diverse contextual settings in line with research ethics and reviewed by the research ethics board. Each case will be analyzed in detail to identify critical success factors, encountered challenges, and employed strategies. The policies surrounding surplus food stores will then be analyzed to assess their impact on successful implementation and their social effect on global communities using the Positive Deviance Model.

This data will be collected using a well-structured, multiple-choice, and open-ended questionnaire among surplus food store owners to assess surplus food shops, policy support, and social impacts at the retail level. The questionnaire will encompass demographic characteristics, business scopes, and challenges encountered during the establishment of zero-waste enterprises as well as national policy frameworks, outcomes, and social impacts. Quantitative data will be analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, and qualitative data will be analyzed using a thematic review to identify recurring themes and patterns. Multivariable relationships will be determined using chi-square or correlation analysis.

Stage 3: Synthesizing Findings and Final Report

Upon completing data collection using the PRISMA methodology (Preferred Reporting Items

for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) to ensure a rigorous and transparent review, and analysis, the synthesized data will be employed to develop actionable policy recommendations and implementation strategies. This synthesis will form the foundation for preparing a final report that summarizes key findings, scopes, and challenges of implementing those shops in other countries, offers targeted recommendations, and outlines implications for policy, practice, and future research directions. Through this approach, the research aims to provide clear guidance for policymakers, businesses, and community stakeholders, facilitating informed decision-making and advancing efforts to enhance food waste reduction, promote social equity, and support global environmental sustainability initiatives.

Goals and Objectives: (Up to 500 words)

The goal of this research is to provide future businesses and policymakers with actionable recommendations on specific strategies in surplus food redistribution to enhance food waste reduction, promote social equity, and support environmental sustainability globally. With this project, we aim to enhance global efforts toward food waste reduction and achieving sustainability targets by providing specific strategies for surplus food consumption.

Despite the abundance of literature on food waste reduction, notable gaps remain in understanding the interplay between national policy frameworks, the successful implementation of surplus food stores, and their social impacts on communities across the globe. Therefore, this research project aims to fill these gaps by comprehensively investigating the implementation strategies, policy frameworks, and social impacts of surplus food stores.

Our proposal aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Assess and evaluate current policies and regulations supporting the implementation of surplus food stores across various countries through a systematic literature review (SLR).
- Identify regulatory barriers, gaps, and inconsistencies in policy frameworks that hinder the widespread adoption of surplus food store initiatives through literature analysis and surveys.
- Identify key factors that may hinder the implementation of surplus food stores worldwide through surveys in the planned case studies.
- Gain knowledge on successful surplus food stores to analyze the critical success factors, encountered challenges, and strategies employed to establish businesses achieving food-waste reduction goals.
- Investigate how surplus food stores contribute to improved access to nutritious food, enhance community engagement, and promote sustainable consumption patterns through literature, policy, and case study analysis.
- Develop and provide comprehensive recommendations for best practices, policy adjustments, and potential implementation of surplus food store concepts across the globe to reduce food waste and promote sustainability.

These are the Research questions (RQs) we set out to answer with our project:

1. **Policy Frameworks and Regulatory Environment:**
 - RQ1: What are the existing policies and regulations supporting the implementation of surplus food stores across various countries?

- RQ2: What regulatory barriers, gaps, and inconsistencies hinder the widespread adoption and success of surplus food store initiatives?
- 2. Implementation Strategies:**
- RQ3: What are the key success factors and strategies contributing to the successful implementation of surplus food stores in different geographical and socio-economic contexts?
 - RQ4: What challenges do surplus food store owners face during the establishment and operation of their businesses?
 - RQ5: What are the scopes of these businesses across the world considering the geographical and economic contexts?
- 3. Social Impacts and Environmental Sustainability:**
- RQ6: How do surplus food stores contribute to food security and improved access to nutritious food for low-income communities?
 - RQ7: What are the social impacts of surplus food stores on community engagement and sustainable consumption patterns?
 - RQ8: How do surplus food stores promote environmental sustainability by reducing food waste at the retail level?
- 4. Best Practices and Recommendations:**
- RQ9: What best practices can be identified from successful surplus food stores to inform future implementation efforts?
 - RQ10: What policy adjustments are necessary to facilitate the broader adoption of surplus food stores globally?

Transformative potential:

The transformative potential of this research lies in its ability to address the critical issue of food waste at the retail level. By investigating surplus food stores and their role in reducing food waste, this research has the potential to significantly influence food security, sustainability, and environmental stewardship. Through a comprehensive analysis of successful case studies, policy frameworks, and social impacts, this research aims to identify and disseminate effective strategies for establishing and operating surplus food stores globally.

Implementing these strategies can lead to substantial reductions in food waste, decreased greenhouse gas emissions, and conservation of valuable resources such as water and energy. Moreover, surplus food stores provide affordable food options, thereby enhancing food access for low-income communities and promoting social equity. The research also aims to offer actionable policy recommendations, which can guide policymakers and businesses in creating supportive environments for surplus food stores.

Ultimately, this research seeks to drive systemic change in the food retail sector, fostering a shift towards more sustainable consumption patterns and efficient food distribution systems. By bridging knowledge gaps and promoting best practices, it has the potential to contribute significantly to global sustainability goals and create a more equitable and environmentally responsible food system.

Literature review

Food waste poses a substantial global challenge with significant economic, environmental, and social consequences. FAO estimates that one-third of all food produced globally, amounting to 1.3 billion tons annually, is wasted (FAO, 2011). Retailers play a crucial role in this waste through practices like overstocking due to inaccurate demand forecasting and discarding food with visual imperfections or nearing expiration dates (LinkRetail, 2023).

To achieve *UN SDG 12.3*, which aims to halve per capita global food waste at the retail level by 2030, it is essential to address the retail sector's role in food waste reduction. Retail chains in concentrated markets have significant influence over food production and quality standards. (UN, 2023; UNGA, 2015).

When prevention isn't possible, food donation is the top priority in the waste hierarchy (WRAP, 2017; Huang et al., 2021). Supermarkets, with their high turnover rates, are key points for collecting and redistributing surplus food. However, only 2-10% of unsold food is donated in European countries (Lebersorger and Schneider, 2014; Parfitt et al., 2016; Eičaitė et al., 2022).

Surplus food stores have emerged as an innovative solution. These stores sell surplus, overproduced, mislabeled, or near-expiry products at reduced prices, reducing waste and providing affordable food options to consumers, especially low-income communities. Examples like *WeFood* in Denmark, the UK's *Company Shop*, and *LetsSaveFood* in Belgium have demonstrated significant reductions in food waste while promoting sustainable consumption patterns (WeFood, 2016; Let's SaveFood, 2021; Saxena et al., 2018).

The success of surplus food stores depends on effective inventory management, community engagement, and supportive local regulations. Advanced inventory management and demand forecasting can minimize overstocking and ensure effective redistribution of surplus food. Community engagement fosters consumer acceptance and participation in food waste reduction initiatives. Dynamic pricing strategies encourage the sale of near-expiry products, reducing waste and offering cost-effective options for consumers (Pimentel et al., 2022).

Effective policies are crucial for surplus food store operations. They can incentivize businesses to donate surplus food, streamline redistribution processes, and provide tax benefits for food donations. However, their effectiveness varies widely. Inconsistent regulations, lack of incentives, and bureaucratic hurdles often hinder the broader adoption of surplus food stores (Pimentel et al., 2022). Supportive policy frameworks in countries like Denmark and the UK have facilitated surplus food stores through legislation, public-private partnerships, and consumer education programs aimed at reducing food waste (WeFood, 2016; Saxena et al., 2018). Conversely, regions with less supportive policies face logistical difficulties, high operational costs, and limited public awareness (Lebersorger and Schneider, 2014).

Existing literature highlights the potential of surplus food stores to address retail-level food waste. Despite efforts to combat food waste, gaps remain in understanding how policy frameworks, implementation strategies, and social impacts, particularly on marginalized communities, interact globally (Pimentel et al., 2022). Successful implementations underscore the importance of supportive policies, effective inventory management, and community engagement. However, broader adoption requires overcoming regulatory and logistical

challenges. Further research is needed to explore these factors in diverse contexts and develop comprehensive strategies for global implementation of surplus food stores.

Briefly describe how your research is transformative in scope

Our project “Opportunities and Constraints to Surplus Food Store Implementation” will investigate the implementation strategies and policies of surplus food stores globally to effectively reduce food waste. Surplus food stores offer a solution to the problem of food waste by redistributing near-expiry or surplus food, but their adaptation is currently limited to a few European countries, impacting the potential benefits..

The goal is to contribute to global sustainability by reducing food waste through effective surplus food store strategies. We will do this by assessing current policies and regulations supporting surplus food stores; identifying key factors and challenges in implementing surplus food stores; and developing policy recommendations to enhance food waste reduction. The scope includes policy and literature review, case studies, surveys, data analysis, and providing recommendations. However, implementation of these recommendations to establish (new) stores or define new policy frameworks falls beyond our scope.

Workplan

The main tasks and activities include: conducting a literature review; performing a policy analysis; identifying and analyzing case studies; designing and distributing surveys; collecting and analyzing data; and drafting a final report with recommendations.

We plan to conduct the research between November 2024 and October 2025, as demonstrated in the Gantt chart and timeline outlining the schedule and tasks. Important milestones are the completion of the literature review (February 2025), finalizing the policy analysis (May 2025), completing the case studies data collection (May 2025), and finishing the final report (October 2025).

The work plan can be further defined as follows:

- Project planning and design: *further defining the research objectives, scope and necessary resources for the study.*
- Identification of cases: *Select and review successful surplus food store cases from various countries across the globe.*
- Survey design: *Develop data collection instruments, including questionnaires for surplus food store owners.*
- Literature review: *Conduct a systematic literature review (SLR) on surplus food stores, food waste, and redistribution strategies.*
- Policy review May 2025: *Analysis of national legal frameworks and policies regarding food waste, food safety and hygiene, and waste redistribution strategies like surplus food stores across the globe.*
- Research Ethics Review of Survey Tools: *Obtain research ethics approval for survey tools and case study protocols.*
- Survey distribution: *Distribute surveys to the identified surplus food store owners through online services, including email, LinkedIn, Facebook etc.*
- Data collection: *Collect data obtained through the case study questionnaires.*
- Data analysis: *Analyze the collected data using statistical and thematic analysis methods as described in the methodology.*

- Report writing: *Synthesize findings and draft the research report.*
- Policy recommendation and implementation strategies: *Develop actionable policy recommendations and implementation strategies.*
- Submit for review: *Submit the final report for review to relevant organizations and associations.*
- Review, incorporate feedback, and finalize report: *Review feedback, make necessary revisions, and finalize the report for distribution.*

Potential risks and challenges can be found in delays in data collection, due to late or incomplete data; difficulty in accessing high-quality, reliable data from surplus food stores across different countries as not all stores or regions may maintain comprehensive records; variations in food waste policies and regulatory frameworks across different countries, complicating comparative analysis; low response rates from surplus food store owners, which may limit representativeness of survey data; and effectively translating research findings into actionable policy recommendations that are feasible and impactful.

We will mitigate these risks by building buffer time into the timeline, sending requests to a large number of surplus food stores, and maintaining flexibility in the research design. To increase the survey response rate, we will design engaging and concise surveys, offer incentives for participation, and emphasize the importance of the study to potential respondents. To ensure effective policy recommendations, we will engage with policymakers and stakeholders throughout the research process to ensure recommendations are feasible.

Our success criteria include timely completion of each milestone, as determined in the timeline and Gantt chart, collection of high-quality data, and provision of actionable recommendations to key stakeholders. To achieve our goals, we will hold regular progress meetings with the members of the team to provide feedback and check in on the progress, thoroughly analyze the research findings, and request feedback from experts.

By following this work plan, the research project will be systematically structured, ensuring thorough investigation, analysis, and recommendations based on findings to contribute significantly to the reduction of food waste and the promotion of global sustainability.

References:

1. Dou Z, Ferguson JD, Galligan DT, Kelly AM, Finn SM, Giegengack R. Assessing US food wastage and opportunities for reduction. 2016. *Global Food Security*;8:19-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2016.02.001>
2. Eičaitė O., Baležentis T., Ribašauskienė E., Morkūnas M., Melnikienė R., & Štreimikienė, D. 2022. Food waste in the retail sector: A survey-based evidence from Central and Eastern Europe. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2022.103116>
3. Facchini E., Iacovidou E., Gronow J., & Voulvoulis N. 2018. Food flows in the United Kingdom: The potential of surplus food redistribution to reduce waste. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association*, 68(9), 887–899. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2017.1405854>
4. FAO. 2011. *Global food losses and food waste – Extent, causes and prevention*. Rome

5. FAO. 2019. The State of Food and Agriculture 2019. Moving forward on food loss and waste reduction. Rome. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.
6. Huang I. Y., Manning L., James K. L., Grigoriadis V., Millington A., Wood V., & Ward S. 2021. Food waste management: A review of retailers' business practices and their implications for sustainable value. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125484>
7. Kulikovskaja, V., & Aschemann-Witzel, J. 2017. Food Waste Avoidance Actions in Food Retailing: The Case of Denmark. *Journal of International Food & Agribusiness Marketing*, 29(4), 328–345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08974438.2017.1350244>
8. Lebersorger S., Schneider F. 2014. Aufkommen an Lebensmittelverderb im österreichischen Lebensmittelhandel. Endbericht im Auftrag der ECR-Arbeitsgruppe Abfallwirtschaft https://www.ecr.digital/wp_content/uploads/2016/09/Aufkommen_an_Lebensmittelverderb_im_Oesterr_Lebensmittelhandel.pdf
9. LetsSaveFood. 2021. Voedsel over? <https://letssavefood.be/actie/>
10. LinkRetail. 2023. Food Waste Management: The Overall Impact of Food Waste in The Retail Sector. <https://linkretail.com/the-overall-impact-of-food-waste-in-the-retail-sector/>
11. PACE. 2018 Denmark against food waste <https://pacecircular.org/denmark-against-food-waste>
12. Parfitt J., Woodham S., Swan E., Castella T., Parry A. 2016. Quantification of Food Surplus, Waste, and Related Materials in the Grocery Supply Chain. https://wrap.org.uk/sites/default/files/2020-10/Quantification-of-food-surplus-and%20waste-in-the-grocery-supply-chain_0.pdf
13. Pimentel B., Misopoulos F., Davies J. 2022. A review of factors reducing waste in the food supply chain: The retailer perspective, *Cleaner Waste Systems* (3), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clwas.2022.100028>.
14. ReFed. 2023. Food Waste Monitor. https://insights-engine.refed.org/food-waste-monitor?break_by=sector&indicator=tons-surplus&view=detail&year=2022
15. Riesenegger L., Santos M. J., Ostermeier M., Martins S., Amorim P., & Hübner A. 2023. Minimizing food waste in grocery store operations: Literature review and research agenda. *Sustainability Analytics and Modeling*, 3, 100023.
16. Saxena, Lopamudra & Tornaghi, Chiara. 2018. The Emergence of Social Supermarkets in Britain: Food poverty, Food waste and Austerity Retail.
17. United Nations General Assembly (UNGA). 2015. Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>.
18. United Nations. 2023. The Sustainable Development Goals Report. <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2023/The-Sustainable-Development-Goals-Report-2023.pdf>
19. WeFood Denmark. 2016. Denmark's first-ever surplus food supermarket
20. Waste Resources Action Program. 2017. Food and Drink Material Hierarchy. <http://www.wrap.org.uk/content/why-take-action-legalpolicy-case>

Timeline:

Activity	Projected Date
----------	----------------

Project planning and design November 2024

